

Mechanism of formation of competitiveness of non-Olympic sports

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The article analyzes the competitiveness of non-Olympic sports in Kharkiv. A mechanism for the formation of competitiveness non-Olympic sports are proposed.

Purpose: develop a mechanism for the formation of competitiveness of non-Olympic sports.

Material & Methods: analysis of literary sources and documents, questioning, organizational modeling, methods of marketing analysis (SWOT-analysis), expert assessment, methods of mathematical statistics. The research was conducted in 5 sports schools in Kharkiv, where non-Olympic sports are cultivated. In total, 136 people participated in the study. The composition of the respondents included: directors, deputy directors, methodologists, trainers.

Results: on the basis of marketing analysis, the mechanism of formation of competitiveness of non-Olympic sports was revealed.

Conclusions: as a result of the study, information on the formation of the competitiveness mechanism for non-Olympic sports has been summarized. A competitiveness mechanism was developed for non-Olympic sports and the effectiveness of the developed mechanism was confirmed using the method of expert assessments.

Keywords: marketing, competitiveness, non-Olympic sports.

Introduction

For non-Olympic sports, the formation of competition policy is currently of particular relevance, given the current state of popularity and the development of non-Olympic sports and the sports industry. Today, there are a large number of private, public, and state physical education and sports organizations, in which non-Olympic sports are cultivated, equipped with the appropriate material and technical base and equipment, and successfully compete in the sports and sports services market. The optimal combination of competitive policy measures, mainly economic and organizational-administrative, provide an opportunity to effectively realize their competitive advantages and ensure high competitiveness in a competitive environment (N. G. Dolbisheva, 2015, N. V. Sereda, 2013; 2015).

Purpose of the study: develop a mechanism for the formation of competitiveness of non-Olympic sports.

Material and Methods of the research

The study used the following research methods: analysis of literary sources and documents, questionnaires, organizational modeling, methods of marketing analysis (SWOT-analysis), expert assessment, methods of mathematical statistics. The study was conducted in 5 of the Children's Sports School of Kharkov, where non-Olympic sports are cultivated. A total of 136 people participated in the study. The structure of the respondents included: directors, deputy directors, methodologists, trainers.

Results of the research

Competition policy is an important component of the economic policy of physical education and sports organizations

for non-Olympic sports and acts as a general guide to action and decision-making that facilitate the achievement of competitive development goals in the market of physical culture and sports. For the formation of competition policy it is necessary to consider the following factors:

- taking into account the factors of external and internal environment that affect competitive development;
- the definition of developmental determinants as a combination of factors that form competitive advantages or create the necessary prerequisites for this;
- the use of modern approaches to the formation of a competitive policy to take into account the characteristics and complexity of the functioning of a sports school for non-Olympic sports in modern economic conditions;
- the choice of modern tools and ways to achieve competitive advantages (T. I. Goncharuk, 2003).

Since the competitive policy of non-Olympic sports is formed in accordance with the nature of the competitive environment and taking into account the existing competitive potential, it is important to understand the interrelation of competition policy with the components of the internal and external environment (Figure).

Competitive marketing policies of sports schools for non-Olympic sports should be aimed at balancing economic relations between other physical education and sports organizations and competitors, forming an effective internal economic mechanism for non-Olympic sports. The process of forming a competitive policy should cover all areas of sports school in non-Olympic sports in order to create stable competitive

positions in the market of physical education and sports services and ensure long-term competitiveness. The basis of an effective competition policy of a sports school in non-Olympic sports is the perfection of the mechanism of formation of competition policy, providing for a system of interrelated methods, means and levers, ensuring the formation of stable competitive positions due to the effective combination of various areas of sports school management. The effectiveness of a competition policy formation mechanism depends on its organizational structure, management structure and style, planning, technology for the provision of physical education and sports services, labor organization and motivation, the availability of quality management policies, etc. schools for non-Olympic sports, in particular, the conjuncture of the consumer market in general and its individual segments (G. A. Fathutdinov 2013; S. V. Gerasimchuk, 2014, A. A. Yarinuk, 2014).

Figure. Mechanism of formation of competitiveness of non-Olympic sports

The mechanism of forming a competitive policy is based on the following main stages: 1) formation of initial information; 2) analysis of the competitive environment; 3) choice of approach to the formation of a competitive policy; 4) the process of forming a competitive policy; 5) assessment of the effectiveness of the competition policy. A necessary condition for increasing the competitiveness of non-Olympic sports is the timely investigation of the degree of influence of macro- and micro-factors on all stages of the implementation of the mechanism (L. L. Antonyuk, 2004; R. Hoye, 2011).

At the first stage of the formation of the initial information is carried out by such departments as economically planned, marketing, accounting, personnel department. Formation of the initial information is as follows:

- 1) study the needs of potential consumers;
- 2) identification of major competitors;
- 3) collection of data on competitors;
- 4) collection of data on the potential consumer;
- 5) choice of the nomenclature of competitiveness criteria.

Next, you should outline the circle of major competitors and collect data about them. Understanding what competitors offer will help management to find ways by which customers will be offered the most appropriate service. For non-Olympic sports one of the important steps in the formation of baseline information is the collection of data on competitors. Com-

petitors have a significant impact on the creation of innovative physical education and sports services and the introduction of new sports. The second stage is characterized by an analysis of the competitive environment of non-Olympic sports, which includes the analysis of internal and external (N. V. Sereda, 2013).

The complexity of the process of formation of competition policy is determined by the number of interrelated controls, the effectiveness of the mechanism of their combination, interaction. The process of forming a competitive policy for non-Olympic sports involves the implementation of the following steps:

- 1) formation of a list of competition laws;
- 2) definition of industry competition rules;
- 3) formation of a policy of interaction with direct competitors;
- 4) formation of a policy of interaction with the main forces in the industry;
- 5) reduction of the results of the implementation of the previous stages to a single form;
- 6) comparison of the consolidated regulations on the available competitive potential and their adjustment;
- 7) definition of the main provisions of the competition policy of non-Olympic sports and their approval by top management.

The final stage in the formation of a competitive policy is the assessment of the effectiveness of the competition policy. In forming a competitive policy, the following principles should be guided by: systematic, comprehensive, effective control, centralization of decision-making, coverage of all functional areas of activity of sports schools for non-Olympic sports.

The main tasks solved by the competition policy are the following: control over the competitive influence in the non-Olympic sports; promoting the development of non-Olympic sports; preventing the reduction of competitiveness.

The methodological basis for controlling the formation of competitive marketing advantages for non-Olympic sports is the classification of factors influencing the formation of competitive advantages, goal-setting mechanism, principles and properties of the management mechanism, the concept of information and analytical support. The competitiveness factors for non-Olympic sports should be transformed into competitive advantages. In this case, competitive advantages should be understood as factors of competitiveness of the region and non-Olympic sports, which ensure its attractiveness and competitiveness in comparison with other territorial formations. Classification of factors is carried out on the basis of a clear and understandable criterion (or criteria), which allows one to uniquely attribute the factor to one group or another. In our study, the competitive advantages and disadvantages were determined using the method of marketing analysis – SWOT analysis. The use of this method allows the generation of new competitive advantages that are concentrated in the region. Due to this, one can not only assess the contribution of each factor to the competitiveness of non-Olympic sports, but also develop a system of private sectoral and functional strategies, as well as a common regional strategy for increasing competitiveness, based on mechanisms for the search and use of internal and external environmental capabilities.

The effectiveness of the developed mechanism for the development of competitiveness for Neo-Olympian sports was due

to the method of expert evaluation. Experts were practitioners of the field of physical culture and sports and research staff, with a total of 20 experts at the expert level. Experts evaluated the 3 groups of expected effects:

- economic: attraction of extrabudgetary funds, expansion of the spectrum of sports school services, increase of investment attractiveness of sports school activity, implementation of the position of "sports manager", activation of advertising activity;
- organizational and managerial increase of the level of efficiency of making managerial decisions, optimization of the mechanism of management of the sports school where non-Olympic sports are cultivated, improvement of the regulatory framework regulating the functioning and development of non-Olympic sports, simplifying the mechanism of building a strategy for the development of neo-Olympian sports, developing a creative approach to organizational -management activities;
- social: strengthening the image of non-Olympic sports, increasing the contingent of those engaged in non-Olympic sports, achieving higher sports results for pupils, increasing the level of competitiveness of non-Olympic sports in the market of sports and fitness services, maintaining the stage of training of athletes and a sustainable contingent.

The main indicators of the social effect from the implementation of the mechanism, the experts determined the following: an increase in the contingent involved in the Youth Sports School (45 points) and increase the competitiveness of the sports school in the market of sports and fitness services (47 points). The results obtained indicate a positive change from the implementation of the mechanism and increase the level of competitiveness.

We note that unanimously experts expect the expansion of the spectrum of physical education and sports services of the sports school from the introduction of the developed mechanism – 1 place. From the following group of indicators, the thoughts of practitioners and scholars fled. Researchers have put the first place in the list – the improvement of the regulatory framework regulating the activity of the Youth Sports School

(47 points), and practitioners – the simplification of the mechanism for building a sports school development strategy (46 points).

The level of consistency of experts in each group was high and confirmed the accuracy of the examination. So, according to the group of indicators of social effect: the coefficient of concordance in science was $W=0,72$; for specialists $W=0,73$. The group of indicators of economic effect: the coefficient of concordance in science was $W=0,71$; for specialists $W=0,72$. In all groups, the coefficient of concordance was $W \geq W_{gr}$, which means consistency of expert opinions.

Conclusions / Discussion

According to the results of the study, a mechanism for the formation of competitiveness for non-Olympic sports was formed. The developed mechanism includes a block of formation, namely the analysis of the macro- and microenvironment of non-Olympic sports. For the effective implementation of the proposed mechanism, the implementation algorithm was defined including: the formation of initial information, the analysis of the competitive environment, the choice of approach to the formation of a competitive mechanism and the analysis of the competitiveness of non-Olympic sports.

An expert evaluation was carried out to confirm the effectiveness of the developed mechanism for the development of competitiveness for the Neolympic sports. Experts determined the main indicators of the social effect from the implementation of the mechanism as follows: an increase in the contingent of those engaged in non-Olympic sports (45 points) and an increase in the competitiveness of non-Olympic sports in the market of physical education and sports services (47 points). The level of consistency of expert opinions in each group was high and confirmed the reliability of the examination. In all groups, the coefficient of concordance was $W \geq W_{gr}$, which means consistency of expert opinions.

Prospects for further research. Develop an organizational plan for the implementation and realization of the developed mechanism in the work of sports schools.

Conflict of interests. The author declares that no conflict of interest.

Financing sources. This article didn't get the financial support from the state, public or commercial organization.

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Received: 04.03.2019.

Published: 30.04.2019.

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